

The Influence of Career Management and Career Development on Turnover Intention: *A Study Based on the Law Firms in Jiangsu, China*

Liu Wanfu

Abstract

Compared with western developed countries, China's lawyer industry is still in the primary stage of development. The turnover intention of legal practitioners is more obvious, and the turnover phenomenon is more common. From the perspective of the reasons for leaving, the actual effect of law firms on the career management of legal practitioners plays an important role. At the same time, most legal practitioners are concerned about their career development status. Especially for young legal practitioners, if they cannot get substantial growth in their work, they will sprout obvious turnover intention. It seems that career management and career development have a significant inhibitory effect on turnover intention. However, it has a strong theoretical and practical value to explore the relationship between the three in detail using quantitative research and empirical analysis. On the one hand, this study addressed the gap for the limitation of the current academic research in related fields; it positively promoted the development of China's lawyer industry. This research will take Jiangsu Province of China as the source of the research samples to analyze the related problems of legal practitioners in Jiangsu law firms. This study explores career management and career development on turnover intention and draws scientific and reliable research conclusions through empirical analysis. Finally, it puts forward relevant suggestions to reduce the turnover intention of legal practitioners in law firms.

IJSB

Accepted 07 June 2021
Published 09 June 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4917123

Keywords: *Legal practitioners, Career management, Career development, Turnover intention, Active personality.*

About Author (s)

Liu Wanfu, Asia Metropolitan University, Malaysia.

INTRODUCTION

Background of Study

The law firm is a very special existence. It has a natural connection with the judiciary, and it is also a special enterprise providing legal services for ordinary people (Liu Xiaoming, 2020). On the one hand, the law is the concentrated embodiment of national ideology (Zeng Liping, 2014). As a form of enterprise organization, law firms maintain a close relationship with national ideology. By providing legal services, law firms protect the legitimate rights and interests of ordinary people, supervise the normal implementation of the law, and promote the good development of the law.

On the other hand, most people know little about the law, but the law has a general impact on various industries and lives. When disputes occur or people have to bear legal responsibility, people often need to seek the assistance of professional lawyers. Therefore, in western developed countries, law firms and lawyers are often respected in society and have a high social status. Of course, this is closely related to the development of the industry. The beginning of the lawyer industry can be traced back to the ancient Greek period (Huang Meiling, 2017), and there were also lawyers in ancient China who specialized in litigation. However, the source of a modern lawyer is originated from the West. Although the lawyer profession in ancient China has always existed, it is quite different from the modern lawyer profession in form and method. In the west, the profession of lawyer appeared as early as in ancient Rome and was recognized by the imperial edict of the rulers of ancient Rome in the third century (Cao Hao, 2020). After a long development period, the modern lawyer industry has a relatively mature form of development in the West.

In contrast, in 1980, China promulgated the "Provisional Regulations on lawyers" to truly re-establish the lawyer system (Qi Biao, 2017). However, after more than 40 years of development, China's lawyer industry is still in a relatively primary stage of development. The number of large-scale law firms is small. Most law firms have a small number of employee and single business scope. Moreover, the turnover of legal practitioners (practising lawyers and practising lawyers) in law firms is very common.

In Jiangsu, where the author is located, the number of lawyers in China ranks third, next only to Beijing and Guangdong. By the end of 2020, 35632 lawyers in the province have a year-on-year increase of 16.98%. Among them, there were 28064 full-time lawyers, accounting for 78.76%, with a year-on-year increase of 10.49%; There were 786 part-time lawyers, accounting for 2.21%, with a year-on-year increase of 20.56%; There were 5580 public lawyers, accounting for 15.66%, with a year-on-year increase of 46.11%; There were 990 lawyers, accounting for 2.78%, with a year-on-year increase of 76.16%; There were 212 legal aid lawyers, accounting for 0.59%, a year-on-year decrease of 1.39%. In terms of age, there are 6453 lawyers aged 29 and below, accounting for 18.11%, 22728 lawyers aged 30-49, accounting for 63.79%, 5760 lawyers aged 50-64, accounting for 16.16%, and 691 lawyers aged 65 and above, accounting for 1.94%. At present, there are 556 lawyers with a doctoral degree, accounting for 1.56%, 6976 lawyers with a master degree, accounting for 19.58%, 27000 lawyers with a bachelor degree, accounting for 75.77%, and 1100 lawyers with a bachelor degree or below, accounting for 3.09%. There are 11332 female lawyers, accounting for 31.8% of the total number of lawyers in the province. The details are shown in Table 1-1

Table 1-1 Statistics of legal practitioners in Jiangsu Province

Category	Number of people	Proportion
Gender		
Male	24300	68.2%
Female	11332	31.8%
Types of employment		
Full-time lawyer	28064	78.76%
Part-time lawyer	786	2.21%
Public lawyer	5580	15.66%
Corporate lawyer	990	2.78%
Legal aid lawyer	212	0.59%
Age		
Under 29 years old	6453	18.11%
30 to 49 years old	22728	63.79%
50 to 64 years old	5760	16.16%
65 and above	691	1.94%
Education		
Doctor	556	1.56%
Master	6976	19.58%
Bachelor Degree	27000	75.77%
Below Bachelor Degree	1100	3.09%

Source: Department of justice of Jiangsu Province

Problem Statement

Among the known reasons for resignation, the main choices of these legal practitioners include three aspects: 1. The job burnout of the lawyer, give up to become a lawyer, transfer to other legal related industries (such as courts, procuratorates), or directly leave the legal industry, enter other industries to work; 2. Establish a law firm of its own; 3. Being invited by other law firms or actively changing to other law firms due to salary and other reasons. It must be pointed out that although the choice after leaving is limited, turnover is a behaviour with complex reasons. Incentive system, interpersonal relationship, leadership style, self-development status, family factors, physical factors and psychological factors may lead to the phenomenon of leaving. So, the fundamental purpose of this research is to find out why the legal practitioners in law firms produce turnover intention. From the current research results, many scholars have analyzed the problem of turnover intention, including:

(1) The impact of law firm management on turnover intention. Management mode is a compound concept. Organizational structure, enterprise system and incentive system are all subordinate to management mode. At the same time, enterprise culture and enterprise atmosphere are directly related to management mode. At present, most scholars are concerned about the impact of the incentive system on turnover intention. Some scholars believe that the lack of an effective incentive system, on the one hand, makes it difficult for employees to have a sense of belonging; on the other hand, it will lead to employees' lack of work enthusiasm and then breed turnover intention (Yang Li, 2012). For law firms, only by establishing a practical incentive system for corporate lawyers can they retain talents and develop business (Li Zonghai, 2013).

(2) Research on the influence of personal factors on turnover intention. No matter what kind of enterprise form, it is the combination of people in the final analysis. There is an obvious relationship between the personality characteristics of employees and turnover intention, which is also applicable to law firms (Zhou Qin, 2010). The research of Wang Ping (2011) and Jiang Tao (2013) also verified this point. However, there is little research on the personal factors of legal practitioners and turnover intention at present. Some scholars, such as Liu Jun (2005), have pointed out that lawyers' personality greatly influences their career

development, and the interruption of many lawyers' careers can even be attributed to their personality defects. In addition, Zhou Haixia (2020) pointed out that the personal ability of young lawyers has great restrictions on their career development, and it is easy to lead to the resignation of young lawyers.

(3) Research on the influence of environmental factors on turnover intention. As an important external factor, environmental factors also have a certain impact on Lawyers' turnover intention. Zhang Fuqiang (2013) pointed out that many lawyers had to change their profession because of tax issues. Sun Wenjun (2015) also pointed out that the institutional environment is closely related to the development of the lawyer industry. The system has a profound impact on the status and overall qualification of the lawyer team and has an important impact on the long-term development of individual lawyers. In addition, many law firms need lawyers to find the source of cases by themselves. This system is particularly unfavourable to the career development of young lawyers and is more likely to become an important incentive for young lawyers to leave (Zhou Haixia, 2020).

Research Objectives

In order to show the research objectives of this research more intuitively, Figure 1-1 summarizes the corresponding relationship between "research questions and research objectives". Corresponding to the five research questions mentioned above, this research sets five research objectives in turn.

Research objective 1: to verify the relationship between career management and career development.

Research objective 2: to verify the influence of career management on turnover intention.

Research objective 3: to verify the influence of career development on turnover intention.

Scope of the Study

First of all, the scope of this study is business administration, so this research is mainly based on the basic theories of management, economics, accounting and so on, through the use of modern management methods and means to carry out effective organizational management and business decision-making, to ensure the survival and development of the organization. Secondly, the specific industry studied in this research is the lawyer industry, and the specific organizational form is the law firm. In addition, the sample of this study comes from Jiangsu Province. This study aims to analyze the influence of career management and career development on turnover intention through the study of Jiangsu law firms.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Turnover Intention

Turnover is a phenomenon of labour mobility. Generally, it is simply defined as employees leaving their existing jobs (Zhang Yi, 2019). Employees' turnover intention can be classified into active turnover and passive turnover (Huang Huaqian, 2019). Active turnover refers to the behaviour that employees decide to terminate the employment relationship with the enterprise because of their inner thoughts. In contrast, passive turnover refers to the behaviour that the enterprise terminates the employment relationship with employees who no longer meet the requirements of the enterprise due to internal layoffs, adjustments, etc. Since individual employees propose active turnover, it has great randomness, and the increase of explicit and implicit costs brought by turnover will have an inestimable impact on enterprises. However, employee turnover is a common phenomenon in today's society, and it is also a normal phenomenon of talent circulation in the human resource market (Zhang Guanglei et al., 2016). Employee turnover can also bring positive effects to the enterprise, such as saving the cost of human resources, preparing for the enterprise to import new

talents, and so on (peak et al., 2010). The research on turnover began in the 20th century. The main object of the research was the male blue-collar workers in manufacturing enterprises. Because the manufacturing enterprises and blue-collar workers made great contributions to the American economy, the scholars at that time focused on this group. With the progress of the times and the continuous improvement of female workers' social status and social role, the research on turnover is gradually transferred to female white-collar workers. Turnover behaviour results from long-term accumulation, and turnover intention is the best variable to predict employee turnover behaviour (Wang Yibao et al., 2013).

Turnover intention refers to the psychological state of an employee before he or she leaves the organization. It intends to leave the organization after a period of careful consideration after working in a specific group (Si Yi, 2019). Some scholars define turnover intention as the possibility of individual employees changing their jobs over time, but it all depends on the category of voluntary resignation. Turnover intention emphasizes an attitude tendency, which has a certain distance from turnover behaviour and does not necessarily lead to turnover (Zhang Kaili et al., 2018). Scholars at home and abroad have different views on the definition of turnover intention, which are summarized in Table 2-1

Table 2-2 Chinese and foreign scholars' definition of turnover intention

Scholar	Viewpoint
Mobley (1977)	Turnover intention comes from the idea of resignation. When employees are dissatisfied with their current job and then have the idea of leaving, they will take the initiative to seek new job opportunities, choose a job that is more conducive to their development among multiple job opportunities, and finally decide to leave. The turnover intention is just the preparation for employees to leave.
Allen (2005)	Turnover intention is a reliable antecedent to help enterprises predict employees' turnover, and it is the turnover idea of looking for new job opportunities after employees are dissatisfied with their current work.
Kim (2012)	Turnover intention is a series of back off behaviours caused by employees' dissatisfaction with their work.
Xia Yanling (2007)	Turnover intention is to show the willingness of employees to withdraw from the current organization, which can well predict the turnover behaviour.
Liu Tingting (2015)	Turnover intention refers to the willingness and thoughts of employees to leave their organizations.
Huang Zhongwei (2016)	Turnover intention is an employee's intention to leave the unit after staying in a specific unit or job for some time.
Liang Qingqing (2018)	Turnover intention is not a real turnover decision, but an uncertain turnover idea exists in employees' minds. Whether employees make turnover behaviour depends on whether they can find new job opportunities that are more conducive to employee development.

Source: Author

According to the research and analysis of relevant literature, it is found that turnover intention is not a single factor but a combination of many factors. Zhou Li (2014) pointed out that age, length of service, and educational background have significant differences for turnover intention through empirical research. The influence of age on turnover intention is not invariable but will change in a certain period. Generally speaking, younger employees have lower turnover intention, and the corresponding turnover intention will increase with age change. However, when they reach a certain age, their turnover intention will decrease; With the increase of educational background, the turnover intention is also gradually increasing. Hao Dashan (2016) believes that the reasons that affect employees' turnover intention can not be classified into self-factors and environmental factors. Self-factors mainly come from employees themselves. For example, less work experience leads to fewer wages

and benefits, which leads to lower job satisfaction and subsequent turnover intention; Environmental factors include social factors and internal factors.

Researchers found that turnover intention is a psychological state of employees based on the previous concepts of turnover intention. Based on the research of domestic and foreign scholars on the dimension of turnover intention, it is found that turnover intention is judged as a single dimension. The scales for measuring employee turnover intention include: employee turnover intention, perception of external job opportunities, the judgment of turnover cost and other evaluative contents, but the questions expressed in the scales are different. Mobley (1979) and others gave an accurate definition of turnover intention. Based on the definition, a single dimension turnover intention scale was designed with four questions.

Career Management

A career is a continuous and dynamic process, a comprehensive process of all career-related behaviours and mental states, and a carrier of career choice, change and goal. Career management, that is, employees' perception of the impact of organizational career management measures on their career development, is the process and activity of the organization from the perspective of employees, which aims to develop employees' potential and promote their career development. Career management plays an important role in the human resource management of modern enterprises. It is a continuous management process for enterprises to help their employees design career plans that consider their development and the needs of strategic enterprise development and help them implement the plans.

Career management continuously meets the needs of employees and enterprises through a series of dynamic management activities. From the perspective of individual employees, the realization of their career development plan needs their continuous efforts and in-depth understanding of themselves, including their knowledge, skills, learning ability, interests, values, etc. Employees should have in-depth research on the content of each occupation and the choice of occupation to make their own career goals and constantly improve their career development plans in the process implementation; For enterprises need to disclose their development strategies, goals, policies and other information to employees, so that employees can better understand the company's employment needs, and then adjust their self-development plans. At the same time, enterprises should do a good job guiding employees to carry out personal career management, optimizing career development channels, doing a good job in training, salary assessment and career information disclosure to help employees implement career development plans. The final result is that the goal of individual employees and the organisation's goal is organically combined and ultimately achieve a win-win situation between individual employees and the enterprise.

Previous research on career management and turnover intention

The research on the relationship between organizational care management and turnover intention has some achievements in the general research of the non-legal service industry or the non-targeted industry. Some of these studies directly or indirectly confirmed the relationship between organizational care management and employee turnover intention. Long Lirong (2002) believes that organizational care management is significantly correlated with organizational commitment, job performance, job security and job satisfaction. This study takes the hotel industry as an example. According to the empirical research, organizational care management has an important positive impact on employees' career commitment, organizational commitment, job involvement, job performance and career satisfaction. The research shows a significant negative correlation between organizational

career management and employees' turnover intention. However, it is a pity that, at present, there are few kinds of literature on the relationship between turnover intention and career management of legal practitioners in law firms. Researchers can only understand the relationship between career management and turnover intention from other aspects. This study innovatively introduces career management to the research of law firms' legal practitioners' turnover intention based on the current research gap.

Career Development

From the micro perspective, career development reflects employees' career progress in a specific career stage, which is the key part of career development theory. Graen et al. (1997) defined the concept of employee career development as the speed at which members gradually flow in the direction of value-added according to the corresponding work sequence. Whitely (1991) defined career development as employees' gaining more authoritative status, higher salary level, broader work authority and higher position promotion. As Christy (2006) defined, career development is the growth opportunity and development opportunity that employees will realize in the current organization. It is mainly to shoulder more important responsibilities, face more severe work challenges, improve work ability and enrich their own work experience. Loscertales (2007) defined career development as the ability of employees to obtain various resources within the organization and promote their higher social status. Yuan Qinghong et al. (2008) affirmed the previous scholars' definition that career development is the career development that employees will achieve within the organization and further divided career development into two dimensions: structural growth and content growth. Weng Qingxiong et al. (2009) defined the concept of career development for the first time in their research. They divided it into two aspects, namely, career development within an organization and career development between organizations, in which career development within an organization refers to the career development speed of employees in the current organization, Inter-organizational career development refers to the career development that employees obtain from the flow between different organizations.

Although there is little literature on career development theory, with the deepening of boundaryless career theory, researchers begin to pay attention to the influence of career development on employee turnover behaviour and have made some research results. Herriot (1994), open and Christopher (1994) found that fair treatment in organizational career management and organizational development orientation significantly affects individual career progress. Weng Qingxiong (2008) studied the direct relationship between the two and demonstrated the negative effect of career development on turnover intention; There are also studies on the relationship between career development and turnover intention of knowledge workers. The study concludes that knowledge workers' career development and turnover intention are significantly negatively correlated (Pang Wenhui, 2011). The research from the perspective of job type confirmed that Huang Yunjuan (2011) found that career development and turnover intention negatively affected the sales staff.

METHODOLOGY

The research process of this study is divided into four stages. First, preparation. In this stage, we mainly focus on theoretical learning, absorbing the existing research results and related theories to determine the research methods of this study, and put forward the corresponding research hypotheses according to the research objectives. Second, data collection and collation. This stage will focus on preparing and verifying the questionnaire for empirical analysis, and through the questionnaire survey, obtain and sort out the data information. Third, data analysis. In this stage, we mainly deal with the data obtained from the questionnaire survey, verify the research hypothesis proposed in this study through

empirical analysis, and get the corresponding research conclusions. Fourth, thinking and analysis. This research analyzes the research conclusions and puts forward corresponding suggestions combined with the actual situation.

Population, Sampling, and Unit of Analysis

This study takes the law firms in Jiangsu Province as the research object, so the samples of this study are all from the law firms in Jiangsu Province. As mentioned in the first chapter, by the end of 2020, there are 2187 law firms in Jiangsu Province, including 1973 partnership firms and 214 individual firms. At the same time, there are 1238 law firms with less than ten lawyers, 800 law firms with 10 to 30 lawyers, 79 law firms with 30 to 50 lawyers, 56 law firms with 50 to 100 lawyers, and 14 law firms with more than 100 lawyers.

Firstly, 214 individual law firms were excluded from the sample. The so-called individual law firm is an organizational form of the law firm. It is a lawyer's practice organization invested by a lawyer. The investment of this organization is not less than 100000 yuan, and the individual investment lawyer bears unlimited liability. On the one hand, we exclude this kind of law firm because the scale of individual law firms is generally small, often with only a few lawyers, especially in some remote cities, individual law firms even have only one lawyer in essence. Therefore, this kind of law firm often does not have the concept of promotion, which is not suitable for this study. On the other hand, due to an unlimited responsibility system, the management mode of an individual law firm is quite different from that of a modern enterprise organization. The management power of individual law firms is highly centralized and often presents a single performance and limited-service scope, so it is not suitable for this study.

To sum up, the final sample size of this study is 778 law firms with 10 to 30 lawyers, 72 law firms with 30 to 50 lawyers, 55 law firms with 50 to 100 lawyers, a total of 905. However, to prevent excessive sample size, this study selects four cities with a GDP exceeding one trillion according to the GDP ranking of Jiangsu Province. The selected cities are Suzhou, Nanjing, Wuxi and Nantong. This study selected 12 law firms from each of the four cities (3 law firms with 10-30 people, 3 law firms with 30-50 people, 3 law firms with more than 50 people and 3 law firms with 50-100 people), and conducted a questionnaire survey on a total of 48 law firms. In this study, 2000 questionnaires were distributed, and all of them were collected. After eliminating the invalid questionnaires such as missing data, circulation and extreme data, the final number of valid questionnaires is 1248, which meets the demand for sample size.

Reliability test

This study adopts SPSS18.0 to test the reliability of the questionnaire, and the final data are shown in Table 3-4. It can be found from Table 3-4 that the Cronbach's values of the subscales of career management, active personality, and turnover intention in the questionnaire are 0.898, 0.901 and 0.853, respectively; The Cronbach's values of fair promotion, providing information, paying attention to training and career cognition were 0.787, 0.753, 0.761 and 0.770, respectively; The Cronbach's a coefficient of all variables are greater than 0.7, which indicates that the internal consistency of the questionnaire is high.

Table 3-1 Reliability Analysis of The Whole Scale

Variable	Cronbach's α value	No. of items	Adopt/Not
Career management (overall)	0.898	15	
Fair promotion	0.787	4	
Information provision	0.753	3	
Pay attention to training	0.761	4	
Professional cognition	0.770	4	
Career development (overall)	0.935	17	
Progress in career goals	0.877	4	Adopt
Professional ability promotion	0.844	4	
Career pay growth	0.921	6	
Social capital accumulation	0.864	3	
Active Personality	0.901	10	
Turnover intention	0.853	3	
The overall scale of the questionnaire	0.947	49	

Source: Author

Validity test

(1) Construct validity. Construct validity, also known as construct validity, refers to the extent to which a test measures the theoretical structure and characteristics to be measured. At the same time, it can also indicate the consistency between the experiment and the theory, whether the experiment measures the hypothetical theory. Consistent with the above, this study also adopted SPSS18.0 to carry out exploratory analysis on the scale and determined the silver structure and silver load. The test results are shown in Table 3-5, Table 3-6 and Table 3-7. As the career development section applies to factor analysis and principal component analysis, the validity test of the career development section will be placed in the chapter of "discriminant validity analysis" later, which is hereby explained.

Table 3-2 Factor Structure And Validity Test (Career Management)

Index name	Item	Factor load	Cronbach α value	KMO value	Explained variance
Promotion equity	C1	0.652	0.898	0.875	66.553%
	C2	0.587			
	C4	0.816			
	C5	0.732			
	C3	0.586			
Information provided	C6	0.662			
	C7	0.808			
	C9	0.646			
Pay attention to training	C10	0.750			
	C11	0.817			
	C12	0.793			
	C13	0.596			
Professional cognition	C14	0.809			
	C15	0.524			
	C16	0.539			

Source: Author

Table 3-3 Factor Structure and Validity Test (Active Personality)

Index name	Item	Factor load	Cronbach α value	KMO value	Explained variance
Active Personality	P1	0.652	0.901	0.895	70.799%
	P2	0.587			
	P3	0.816			
	P4	0.732			
	P5	0.586			
	P6	0.662			
	P7	0.808			
	P8	0.646			
	P9	0.750			
	P10	0.817			

Source: Author

Table 3-4 Factor Structure And Validity Test (Turnover Intention)

Index name	Item	Factor load	Cronbach α value	KMO value	Explained variance
Turnover intention	T1	0.892	0.853	0.716	78.087%
	T2	0.910			
	T3	0.848			

Source: Author

From the data of the above three tables, the validity tests of career management, active personality and turnover intention are all qualified. Among them, the load values of each factor are all above 0.5, KMO values are all above 0.7, and the explained variance values are all above 66%. Therefore, it can be considered that these factor structures are reliable and effective.

Data Analysis Methods

First of all, the number of questionnaires distributed in this study is relatively large, with more than 1000, and the total data value in the sample is more than 10000. Therefore, this study uses SPSS18.0 and other data processing software to summarize all the qualified questionnaires collected in this study and compile relevant tables for intuitive presentation to facilitate the analysis and research of this study. In addition, to complete the predetermined research objectives of this study, this study further analyzes the questionnaire data after sorting it out. This study adopts empirical analysis, using SPSS18.0 and other data analysis software, through regression analysis and other ways to verify the research hypotheses proposed in this study to get the corresponding research conclusions.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Descriptive statistics of samples

In this study, statistical software shows descriptive statistics of the above information, and the statistical results are shown in Table 4-1. According to the table, 54.2% of the effective samples were male, and 45.8% were female, which is slightly less than that of male, which is consistent with the actual situation of law firms. From the age structure of the sample, there is little difference among all age groups. Except for employees over 51 years old, this part of employees is determined from the career development stage, while the largest proportion of 26-30 years old sample is 32.1%. In the family status, unmarried accounted for 32.4%, married accounted for 67.6%, which is consistent with the reality; 33.7% of them have worked for more than ten years, which may be related to the questionnaire collection. From the perspective of education level, the proportion of undergraduates is the highest, accounting for 54.8%, which is also consistent with the reality.

Table 4-1 Sample descriptive statistics

Variable	Content	Number of people	Proportion (%)
Gender	Male	676	54.2
	Female	572	45.8
Age	Under 25	280	22.4
	26-30 years old	400	32.1
	31-40 years old	268	21.5
	41-50 years old	244	19.6
	Over 51 years old	56	4.5
Marital status	Single	404	32.4
	Married, childless	296	23.7
	Married with children	548	43.9
Working years	Less than 3 years	276	22.1
	3-5 years	340	27.2
	6-10 years	212	17.0
	More than 10 years	420	33.7
Education	Below college	44	3.5
	College graduate	304	24.4
	Undergraduate	684	54.8
	Master degree or above	216	17.3
Total		1248	100

Source: Author

Descriptive statistics of variables

Descriptive statistical analysis is to use statistical language to describe the relationship between sample characteristics or sample variables. Due to the many measurement data, it is impossible to reflect the overall characteristics of multiple data from a single measurement data. Descriptive statistics can integrate many data and form a new understanding of the collection of these data. The dispersion trend reflects the dispersion degree of the measured data, which is expressed by the range and standard deviation. The range is the difference between the maximum and minimum extreme values of the measured data. The standard deviation comprehensively reflects the data's dispersion degree and is used together with the average.

Research Objectives One: Career Management and Career Development

Table 4-6 shows the relationship model's fitting indexes between career management and career development. According to the simulation of the impact of career management and career development, χ^2/df is 1.921, which is less than the reference standard value 3. RMR and RMSEA were 0.046/0.065, respectively, which were lower than the reference standard value of 0.08. GFI, NFI, IFI and CFI are all above the reference standard value of 0.9; AGFI is 0.873, greater than the mark value of 0.85. Comprehensively, all the fitting indexes are within the range of reference standard values, which indicates that the model is in good condition and supports theoretical hypotheses.

Table 4-2 Fitting index of relationship model between career management and career development

Model	χ^2/df	RMR	GFI	AGFI	NFI	IFI	CFI	RMSEA
Standard value	<3	<0.08	>0.9	>0.85	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9	<0.08
Structural model	1.921	0.046	0.906	0.873	0.916	0.926	0.926	0.065

Source: Author

Table 4-7 below shows the statistical table of the standardized coefficient of the relationship model between career management and career development. The table shows that the

standardized coefficient of the legal practitioners of Jiangsu law firms to career development is 0.868, P-value is 0.000, reaching the level, which indicates that the relationship model of the influence of career management on career management on career development turnover intention is established.

Research Objective Two: Career Management and Turnover Intention

Table 4-11 below shows the statistical table of fitting indicators of the relationship model between career management and turnover intention. It can be seen from the table that the influence model of career management on turnover intention of legal practitioners in law firms shows that the value of χ^2 / DF is 1.398, which is less than the reference standard value of 3. The RMR was 0.040, less than 0.08. The values of GFI, NFI, IFI and CFI were above the reference standard value of 0.9. In addition, AGFI was 0.866, greater than 0.85, RMSEA was 0.043, less than 0.08. This shows that all the fitting indexes are within the range of the reference standard value, which indicates that the model fits well and supports the theoretical hypothesis.

Table 4-3 Fitting indexes of the relationship model between career management and turnover intention

Model	X2/df	RMR	GFI	AGFI	NFI	IFI	CFI	RMSEA
Standard value	<3	<0.08	>0.9	>0.85	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9	<0.08
Structural model	1.398	0.040	0.913	0.886	0.952	0.986	0.986	0.043

Source: Author

According to the fitting index, the standardized coefficient of career management and turnover intention can be calculated, and the specific value is shown in Table 4-12. It can be found from the table that the standardized path coefficient of career management to turnover intention is -0.887, P-value is 0.000, reaching a significant level. This shows that the model of the relationship between career management and turnover intention is established, and there is a strong correlation between career management and turnover intention. All the above data support hypothesis H2 proposed by this research.

Research Objective Three: Career Development and Turnover Intention

Table 4-16 below is the statistical table of fitting indexes of the relationship model between career development and turnover intention. From the influence simulation of career development and turnover intention, the value of χ^2 / DF is 1.674, which is less than the reference standard value of 3. RMR and RMSEA were 0.031 and 0.056, respectively, which were less than the reference standard value of 0.08. The values of GFI, NFI, IFI and CFI were all above 0.9. The AGFI values were 0.858 and greater than 0.85, respectively. To sum up, all the fitting indexes are within the range of the reference standard value, which indicates that the model fits well, supports the theoretical hypothesis, and can be used for empirical analysis.

Table 4-4 Fitting index of the relationship model between career development and turnover intention

Model	X2/df	RMR	GFI	AGFI	NFI	IFI	CFI	RMSEA
Standard value	<3	<0.08	>0.9	>0.85	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9	<0.08
Structural model	1.674	0.031	0.902	0.858	0.945	0.977	0.977	0.056

Source: Author

According to the fitting index, the standardized coefficient value of the relationship model between career development and turnover intention is calculated, as shown in Table 4-17. As shown from Table 4-17, the standardized path coefficient of career development to turnover

intention is -0.915 , $P = 0.000$, reaching a significant level. This shows that the relationship model of career development to turnover intention is established, and the data support the research hypothesis H3. In the era of boundless career, legal practitioners pay more attention to the current interests and their growth. In organizing career management, law firms need to establish a fair promotion mechanism, provide detailed position information, pay attention to staff training, and help staff self-awareness and other measures. If the legal practitioners can not correctly recognize, understand and actively participate, the benefits of career development brought by career management can not be reflected in themselves. In other words, if the legal practitioners can not correctly recognize the state of their career development, then it can not reflect the benefits of the law firm to carry out career management, and these management measures will be ineffective for the legal practitioners to turn over the intention. Therefore, the career development of legal practitioners is the determinant of their turnover intention. The organizational level of career management measures must be through the legal practitioners' perception of their career development to impact the legal practitioners' turnover intention. In addition, career development plays an intermediary role between career management and turnover intention. Through the analysis, we find that career management has a significant negative impact on the turnover intention of legal practitioners; Career management has a significant positive impact on the career development of legal practitioners; Career development has a significant negative effect on turnover intention.

CONCLUSION

This research explores the relationship between career management, career development, and turnover intention through empirical analysis and questionnaire survey. Through the analysis, this study verified that career management and career development have a significant negative effect on turnover intention, which shows that career management and career development can effectively reduce the emergence and dThrough the analysis, we can see that the structure of career development of legal practitioners in law firms consistently reflects four dimensions: career goal progress, career ability improvement, career reward growth, and social capital accumulation. Among them, social capital accumulation is a new dimension for career development. Although the existing research on the structural dimension of career development has many conclusions, such as one-dimensional theory (ability), two-dimensional theory (internal growth and external growth), three-dimensional theory (ability, promotion, compensation), four-dimensional theory (career goal, ability promotion, promotion, income), its core still focuses on three aspects, namely ability, promotion and income. Ability improvement belongs to internal career development, while promotion and income increase belong to external career development.

There are some differences between this study and the existing research conclusions. One is that promotion and income are reflected in the same dimension: the growth of professional remuneration. In addition, a new dimension is found, that is, the accumulation of social capital. Social capital accumulation, similar to promotion and income, belongs to legal practitioners' external career development. This study focuses on the structural dimension of career development for law practitioners in law firms. The differences in the conclusions mainly come from the differences in the management and operation of law firms and the characteristics of the profession.

The era of boundaryless career brings severe challenges to the organization career management. On the one hand, the career development of legal practitioners has no boundaries. Improving the interdependence between employees and organizations, improving the level of organizational commitment of legal practitioners, and then improving

their loyalty will be major issue that law firms must face in the future for a long time. In addition, if legal practitioners cannot achieve career development in law firms, they will start to look for other growth opportunities. Moreover, after getting good career development, legal practitioners will consider the possibility of leaving once they encounter better career opportunities. Such contradictions exist not only in the legal service industry but also in other industries.

REFERENCES

- Arthur, M. B. (2010). The boundaryless career: a new perspective for organizational inquiry. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 15.
- Arthur, M. B., & Lawrence, B. S. (1984). Perspectives on environment and career: an introduction. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 5(1), 1-8.
- Bai Yanli. (2012). Dynamic development of employee employment relationship perception and its management strategy —— from the perspective of psychological contract theory. *Lanzhou Journal*, (12), 103-108.
- Bai, G. L., Ling, W. Q., & Guo-Hao, L. I. (2011). Research on the relationship between career plateau and job satisfaction, organizational commitment and turnover intention. *Soft Science*.
- By Tian. (2012). Practice lawyer and professional lawyer. *Chinese lawyer*, (08), P. 50-50.
- Chen Yao, & Cao Keliang. (2018). A brief analysis of the concept and type of professional anchor. *Shandong Youth*, (03), 99.
- Cui Hanyue. (2020). Under the background of the new era, employees. *Career management financial circles*, 548(05), 254-255.
- Dai Dandan, Jia Chunyi, Zhang Qi, & Zhu Renying. (2016). Career perception and Career development 、 Turnover intention relationship between employed nurses. *China Public Health*, 32(004), 563-565.
- Defillippi, R. J., & Arthur, M. B. . (2010). The boundaryless career: a competency-based perspective. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 15(4), 307-324.
- Deng Xiaobin. (2018). *A study on the development strategy of QZWD law firms*. (Doctoral dissertation, Jiangxi University of Finance and Economics).
- u Xiaolong. (2011). Analysis of influencing factors of career anchor for college students. *Commercial economy*, (007), 121-122.
- GE Pengqi. (2020). Learn new knowledge, and you will not be out of the bar elite. *Law and Life*, (2), 61-61.
- Gu Jia Jun & Xie Fenghua. (2007). An empirical study on the reasons for employee turnover in small and medium-sized private manufacturing enterprises. *Economic latitude*, (06), 101-103.
- Hao Dashan. (2016). Research on turnover management of new generation knowledge workers. *Shandong Social Sciences*.
- Jiang Yifan. (2020). *A study on the multi-level influence of personality trait and organizational innovation situation on employee Career development*. (Doctoral dissertation, University of Science and Technology of China).
- Jiao Xiaobo & Zhang Xiaobing. (2010). Analysis on the causes of job burnout of female employees in enterprises —— based on the investigation of female employees in Shanghai enterprises. *Journal of Jilin Institute of Industry and Commerce*, (01), 38-43.
- Jing. (n.d.). *The reflection and reconstruction of lawyer management system in China*. (Doctoral dissertation, Hebei Normal University).
- Ke Jianglin, & Sun Jianmin. (2014). effects of psychological capital on job satisfaction, organizational commitment and Turnover intention. *Economic and Management Studies*, (1), 121-128.
- Kim, S. . (2012). The impact of human resource management on state government it employee turnover intentions. *Public personnel management*, 41(2), 257-279.
- Knight, D. K., Crutsinger, C., & Kim, H. J. . (2006). The impact of retail work experience, career expectation, and job satisfaction on retail career intention. Liu Xiaoming. (2020). The mission of lawyers and law firms. *Democracy and the rule of law*, (2), 60-61.
- Liu Yang. (2020). Dual pattern of administrative law enforcement and criminal justice and its consequences —— Take the experience in the field of food and drug supervision as an example.

- Journal of Huazhong University of Science and Technology (Social Sciences Edition)*, 034(001), 93-101.
- Long Lirong, Fang Liluo & Ling Wen. (2002). Enterprise employee self- Career management structure and relationship. *Psychology report*, 35(002), 183-191.
- Lu Liangbiao. (2005). Chinese lawyers in "danger "—— the practice risk of lawyers and their prevention. *Chinese lawyer*, (09), 50-51.
- Luo Xuan, & Wei Xia. (2018). *A study on the relationship between organizational support and knowledge worker Turnover intention from the perspective of work control*. Proceedings of the 13th (2018) China Management Annual Conference.
- Ma Dewei, Yi Yunqing, Feng Muchen, Tian Mei & Shi Junqi. (2009). Active personality and Career management. *Occupation*, (08), 24-24. .
- Mao Changguo & Sun Jianmin. (2013). Study on the harm of uncivilized behaviour in workplace based on active personality regulation. *Journal of Management*.
- Marry. (2017). *An empirical study on the Turnover intention impact of organizational cynicism on the organizational fairness of post-90s technical employees*. (Doctoral dissertation, Hebei University).
- Niu Shuang & Guo Wenchen. (2009). Analysis on the relationship between career adaptability and career success in the age of boundless career. *Journal of Dalian University of Technology (Social Sciences Edition)*, (1), 34-39.
- Orpen, & Christopher. (1994). The effect of time-management training on employee attitudes and behaviour: a field experiment. *Journal of Psychology*, 128(4), 393.
- Pang Wenhui. (2011). Analysis of influencing factors and countermeasures of knowledge-based employee mobility. *Economic Research Guide*, 000(002), 58-59.
- Peak, & Ma Aixia. (2010). Cost-benefit analysis of employee turnover on enterprise. *Management Observation*, (031), 90-91.
- Qin Meihu. (2020). On the survival and development of young lawyers. *Information Weekly*, (011), 11.
- Qing Tao & ao Yulan. (2014). Review and Prospect of career Capital Research. *International Conference on Career Development and Employment Management, 2014*.
- Qu Kejia, Ju Ruihua, Zhang Qingqing. The relationship between college students' active personality, career decision-making self-efficacy and career exploration. *Psychological development and education*.
- Qu Miao-wen. (2015). *The relationship between Career development and Turnover intention: a study of the regulatory effect of personal and organizational values matching*. (Doctoral dissertation, Nanjing Normal University).
- Rong Fengjie. (2013). Explore the Career development and social capital influence mechanism of university administrators. *Journal of Ningxia University (Humanities and Social Sciences Edition)*, 35(006), 109-112.
- Sengupta, S., Sharma, S., & Singh, A. . (2020). Authentic leadership fostering creativity in start-ups: mediating role of work engagement and employee task proactivity. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 9.
- Shan Hongmei, Hu Enhua, Bao quietly & Zhang Maolong. (2015). A study on the influence of organizational status perception level on Turnover intention in non-state-owned enterprises. *Journal of Management*, 012(008), 1144-1153.
- Thompson, & Jeffery, A. . (2005). Proactive personality and job performance: a social capital perspective. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 90(5), 1011-7.
- Tom, Duncan, and, Sandra, & Moriarty. (1999). Commentary on relationship-based marketing communication. *Australasian Marketing Journal (AMJ)*.
- Uhlbien, M. . (2009). Individual Self-Management : Analysis of Professionals ' Self-Managing Activities in Functional and Cross-Functional Work Teams Author (s): Mary Uhl-Bien and George B. Graen Source : The Academy of Management Journal, Vol. 41, No. 3 (Jun., 1998).
- Wang Congying. (2014). *Research on psychological mechanism of turnover behaviour of new generation knowledge workers*. (Doctoral dissertation, Nanjing University).
- Wu Ting, Xiao Ziyun, Lin Qiu Xu & Huang Liangzhi. (2014). A study on the cultural intelligence, cross-cultural adaptation and career success of overseas personnel —— with career capital as the adjustment variable. *Human resources management reviews*.

- Wu Xiaojun. (2006). Analysis of the factors affecting personal career. *Employment of Chinese University Students*, (14), 81-82.
- Xia Yanling. (2007). Analysis of the influencing factors of employee Turnover intention in small and medium-sized private enterprises. *Economics and Management*, 21(001), 52-55.
- Xiang Min & Wang Zhongjun. (2006). On the opposition and integration of quantitative research and qualitative research in psychology. *Journal of Fujian Medical University: Social Sciences Edition*, (02), 51-54.
- Xiang Min, Wang Zhongjun. (2007). Active Personality and Career Success. *Talent Development*, (07):12-14.
- Xie Baoguo & long Lirong. (2008). The influence of career plateau on employee job satisfaction, organizational commitment and turnover intention. *Psychology report*, 40(008), 927-938.
- Xu Maosheng, Nie Shaoqun. (2014). The influence of Career management on employee turnover intention is analyzed empirically —— the intermediary role of employee career pressure. *Science and Technology Plaza*, (07), 155-161.
- Xu Miao. (2019). Analysis on the reasons and countermeasures of employee turnover in modern enterprises. *Modern Economic Information*, (016), 133.
- Yan Shimei. (2010). theoretical interpretation of the reasons for employee turnover in mergers and acquisitions: a literature review. *Journal of Zhejiang University (Humanities and Social Sciences Edition)*, 41(003), 180-189.
- Yang Benli. (2009). The development of Watson's behaviourism theory and its application in modern society. *Northeast University of Finance and Economics*
- Yang Chunjiang. (2013). *Study on the mechanism of work embedding on turnover in Chinese context*. (Northeastern University, Doctoral dissertation,).
- Yang Dongtao, Cao Guonian, & Zhu Wusheng. (2008). Study on the reasons and mechanism of new knowledge workers leaving. *Jiangsu Social Sciences*, (05), 63-67.
- Zhuang Hao. (2019). Suqian law firm management problems and countermeasures. *Yangzhou University*
- Zou Xiaoyan. (2016). *The influence of active socialization behaviour of new employees on Career development —— the role of career capital and organizational support*. (Doctoral dissertation, Southwest University of Finance and Economics).

Cite this article:

Liu Wanfu (2021). The Influence of Career Management and Career Development on Turnover Intention: A Study Based on the Law Firms in Jiangsu, China. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 5(8), 123-138. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4917123>

Retrieved from <http://ijsab.com/wp-content/uploads/788.pdf>

Published by

